

BioMedBridges

WORKSHOP REPORT: A common vocabulary to classify life science resources

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Summary

A one day workshop, organised by [ELIXIR](#), [BioMedBridges](#) and [RDA](#), was held on 16 October 2014 in Brussels to kick-start agreement on a common 'topics' vocabulary to classify resources in the life sciences domain, including databases, tools, courses, training materials, meetings, jobs and publications. Service providers and registries currently use different vocabularies to classify resources. From the user point of view, a common topics vocabulary would enhance the ability to find related resources of interest. From the provider point of view, a common vocabulary would be an important step to facilitate the interoperability of existing resources and significantly increase the impact and reach to different user communities. Workshop participants, who also discussed use cases and how agreement on high-level terms would positively impact the different communities, included representatives of societies, networks, institutes, organisations, research infrastructures and projects, as well as BioMedBridges project partners and members of several ELIXIR Nodes.

The workshop, both in terms of participation and the reaction in the wider community, revealed that there is widespread interest in and support for the development of a common topics vocabulary, and it provided the basis and strategies for moving forward. While there was general agreement on the aims and content of the vocabulary proposed at the workshop, there were indications that the structure may need further discussion. Ultimately, wide adoption is necessary to realise potential impact. To achieve this, a critical mass of initial resources needs to adopt the vocabulary to be able to demonstrate its utility with the first use cases. Funding will eventually be necessary to further develop and adapt the vocabulary itself as well as to develop further applications.

Workshop aims and background

Vision: A common vocabulary to classify resources in the life sciences¹

Rafael Jimenez

A common vocabulary can be used to describe resources: Tools, Data repositories, Events, Courses/Meetings/workshops etc., Standards, Experts (e.g. Trainers, curators, domain experts, etc.), policies, materials, jobs, publications, etc.

Example annotations from a vocabulary used to classify resources:

- Keywords: e.g. Clustal
- Type of resource: e.g. Software or Training course
- Scientific domain: e.g. Phylogenetics
- General activity: e.g. Sequence alignment
- Object of Study: e.g. Pathogens

The categories in question for the common vocabulary are scientific domain, general activity and object of study. Keywords are too specific/diverse and will be hugely dependent on and driven by the community using the respective resource, and “type of resource” does not add information to the the resource entry, or could even add confusion.

An example for the different tags used by different registries for the same resource include e.g. the entry for IntAct in the MIRIAM registry (tags used: protein, interaction) and BioSharing.org (tags: molecular interactions, protein-

¹

http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/workshops/aims_of_the_workshop_-_rafael_jimenez_02.pdf

protein interaction, protein-small molecule interaction, protein-DNA interaction, protein-RNA interaction, gene ontology annotations, dtrains, domain (via InterPro), literature citations, binding domain position, experimental tags, gene nomenclature, gene product names, controlled vocabularies, free text description, protein, interaction).

In addition to using different vocabularies to classify resources, service providers and registries do not share a minimum set of fields (information about resources/metadata) to describe resources. Together with a common vocabulary, agreement on Minimum Information About a Resource (MIAR), defining common fields to describe resources in life sciences, would be desirable as a first step to facilitate contextualization, which would improve usability, resource discoverability and integration.

Contextualising resources in the life sciences domain using minimal metadata²

Susanna-Assunta Sansone

The challenge is that there are many, diverse and dispersed resources, making it difficult for the user to find resources that are relevant to them. In order to support users, facilitate research and maximise the impact of available resources, they need to be made more discoverable. These resources (see introduction to theme below) also uses different common vocabulary to annotate topics. If they were to use a common vocabulary, they would need funds to map or retrofit the current terms, but also funds to participate to the collaborative development of this common vocabulary.

Using a common vocabulary and minimum set of metadata to describe resources will improve usability and discoverability of resources by users and aid interoperability of resources. Based on annotation with common topics, different types of resources can be pulled together - for example, a user looking for a

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http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/workshops/contextualising_resources_in_the_life_sciences.pdf

metabolomics data might receive suggestions for relevant tools, standards, courses, training materials or job offers etc.

Concrete steps required to drive this work forward are:

1. Common topics vocabulary
2. Minimum set of fields
3. Exposure of metadata
4. Integration of metadata
5. Applications to search/find
6. Applications to discover/contextualize

Introduction of resources and terminologies currently used

Below are links to presentations of different services that aim to enhance discoverability of resources as well as systems for high-level annotation currently in use.

[ELIXIR Tools & Data Services Registry](#) (Kristoffer Rapacki)

[toolinfowarehouse](#) (Matus Kalas)

[SeqWIKI and MetaBase](#) (Dan Bolser)

[BioSharing](#) (Susanna Sansone)

[BioCatalogue](#) (Niall Beard)

BioRegistry (Marie-Dominique Devignes)

[identifiers.org](#) (Camille Laibe)

[EMBL-EBI resources](#) (Bren Vaughan)

[The EDAM vocabulary](#) (Jon Ison)

Topics mapping

Mapping of topics from training providers and registries³

Cath Brooksbank

There is a challenge to providing training for biomedical research: the traditional approach provides training by discipline, e.g. Biology, Pharmacology, Chemistry, Pharmacy, Immunology, Medicine. This results in duplication of professional development within silos with limited sharing of knowledge between them. In contrast, 21st century life science research involves for example predictive science, translational medicine, personalised healthcare, open innovation, and big data, all of which cross between or cover several “traditional” scientific disciplines. To address the training needs resulting from this, the silo-based approach does not work any longer.

The specific bioinformatics training challenge is data analysis, which is the major bottleneck to research in the molecular life sciences. There are an estimated 500,000 scientists in Europe; each is potentially a user of life science data resources. However, many molecular life scientists are unaware of these resources or feel under-qualified to make the most of them for their research.

Crucially, the resources are useless unless scientists know how to use them, and training courses are useless unless people know how to find them.

To be truly useful, it is important to develop a system that:

- Gives course seekers what they are expecting when they come to the course providers’ website, aggregates courses in ways that are logical to course seekers
- Improves discoverability of courses for the wider user community and
- Allows course providers to enter course information once and once only

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http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/workshops/cath_brooksbank_topic_ontology_141016.pdf

To achieve this, consistent categorisation of course topics is needed. In a piloting effort as part of the [on-course training portal](#), which aims to provide training resources to users across the life sciences, EMBL-EBI course tags were mapped to topics in EDAM⁴. This revealed the need for having “minimum information about a course” which, together with consistent annotation using a controlled vocabulary, will contribute to better automated exchange of course metadata between course providers and course aggregators and enable more intuitive searching for courses (including ‘find more courses like this one’).

Ultimately, if the use of the controlled vocabulary is applied to other areas beyond training, it will be possible to link training to services: e.g. a user might be presented with suggestions like ‘if you’re interested in this course, you might be interested in these services...’.

Mapping topics across life-science resources⁵

Stephanie Suhr

In preparation for the workshop, 20 volunteers mapped the terms or vocabularies used by 24 resources to the EDAM controlled vocabulary (227 topics). Mapping revealed that EDAM could provide a solid basis for a topics vocabulary and that there was already good agreement between the terms used by the individual resources: about 82% of possible (“mappable”) terms from the resources were successfully mapped to the topics from EDAM. Difficulties encountered included for example ambiguous terms and terms used by individual resources being too specific.

It was possible to identify a significant number of new terms not previously covered in EDAM (67 topics, ca. 23% of total terms needed) that might be included in a new iteration of the topics vocabulary. While most of the new terms suggested were in the areas of “biology” and “medicine” which, together with

⁴ <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btt113>

⁵

http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/workshops/mapping-effort_steffisuhr.pdf

“computer science”, already make up the vast majority of terms in EDAM, a number of the resources mapped also needed terms under the categories “laboratory techniques”, “chemistry” and other areas. Overall, the mapping exercise indicated that the approach of driving adaptations of a topics vocabulary via the needs (topics used) of resources would be both straightforward and present an objective approach to optimising it.

Future development

Strategies to adopt and develop the common topics vocabulary⁶

Niklas Blomberg

Four main challenges were highlighted:

1. With so many stakeholders (resources, registries, communities...), who decides on the overall strategy?
2. Should efforts be combined or would it be preferable to start fresh?
3. Scope: what is sensible and where to draw the line?
4. What are the incentives (value, impact, funding) and use cases to drive adoption?

Breakout sessions: topics inspection

Workshop participants were asked to examine the proposed list of topics based on EDAM and extended with new terms from the mapping exercise described above. Below is a summary of the main feedback received while including some

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http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/workshops/intro_x2_-_niklas.pdf

specific examples for illustration (full detail is included in the “Living document”⁷ prepared during the workshop).

Coverage

- The way ***some scientific domains or specific areas are represented in the vocabulary needs more work*** (too vague, not detailed enough, missing terms)
- BUT a single artefact encompassing the broadest scope is not sensible or viable

Structure

- There are ***potential problems in introducing a hierarchy***: it suggests that things are structured when they may not be or when parent-child relationships are unsuitable; this can lead to confusion
- For example: medical informatics is under medicine while bioinformatics and cheminformatics are under “computer science”, they might need to be found from ; medical disciplines vs. conditions is unclear (pathology only has a very small number of topics, most conditions and diseases needed to be mapped to medical disciplines); biomedical science (including “sample collections”) is listed as a child under medicine, which may be unsuitable
- Some topics can also have multiple parenthood - but need to ***keep complex relationship between topics to a minimum***
- The ***right level of granularity - also across disciplines - is important***. For example, medicine is mostly tier 1-2, biology is down to levels 1-4: need to be consistent. Different resources may need different levels of granularity for complete annotation
- Need to ***balance granularity and conciseness*** of the vocabulary

⁷ tinyurl.com/OurTopicsNotes

- The root of the proposed list of topics seems to be based on classical academic roles, e.g. librarian, technical assistant, scientists - this may lead to difficulties when choosing topics in interdisciplinary contexts
- The central list of topics should only include “core terms”; additional terms should be available in additional/custom modules with different access levels

Topics

- There was some **confusion over what constitutes a “topic”**: e.g. the top-level of EDAM contains both domains and techniques
- The proposed vocabulary **duplicates some terms** that are available in other widely used ontologies; such terms should instead be imported from these other sources, maintaining ID and provenance information
- A topic should identify only ONE type of activity, e.g. “Data acquisition and deposition” should be “data acquisition” and “data deposition”
- Only “high-level” (widely recognised, common) operations should be included
- Specialised concepts should be modelled as narrow synonyms

Misplaced and missing terms

- There are some **misplaced terms and missing terms**, for example “text mining” should be under “computer science”, “model organisms” need to be separate from taxonomy, “data analysis” shouldn’t be under “data management”
- Missing terms e.g. under computer science (programming languages, databases) are in scope of the Software Ontology
- Transcriptomics, metabolomics, etc. are all scattered: group them all together under omics

Sustainability and further development

Quality criteria, value and maintenance

Involving the community

- The common vocabulary should be **responsive to the requirements of different communities** and their specific use-cases, e.g. typing keywords into search boxes, browsing a hierarchy, curation practices etc.
- It is critical to have early adopters; going forward, adopters must be part of the further development process of the vocabulary
- **Community participation** must be reflected in the **governance of the vocabulary**

Ensuring quality and managing expectations

- The vocabulary must have **clear quality criteria**, e.g. “this term needs to be included because it enables us to do X”
- Need a clear **statement concerning the value** to be delivered by the vocabulary
- Need a **plan to leverage existing resources**, e.g. from libraries such as MeSH, PubMed keywords, etc., and community ontologies such as NIF, BioSitemaps, OBI etc.
- The primary users of the vocabulary are curators and developers, so it must serve their needs
- There is a tooling requirement to support easy annotation by curators and developers: need *lightweight* tools that are very easy to use, with very compelling reasons to do it
- A useful *and* usable controlled vocabulary of terms will allow machines to connect semantically annotated information but, importantly, also allow HUMANS to select terms from a manageable list, and use them to describe their information/content

Extending the vocabulary

- Need a formal **mechanism to identify necessary extensions**; extensions could also be implemented as auxiliary vocabularies
- Extension of the vocabulary could be based on identifying the main areas not covered, based on recommendations from expertise assembled at the workshop
 - include resources from those domains: invite them to submit their list of topics/terms used → list of topics is driven by vocabularies used by the resources included (objective, utilising expertise/knowledge of user needs of individual resources)
- Suggested inclusion of new terms can go either of two ways:
 - rare term in vocabulary used by a single (or small number of) resource(s): community-specific add-on or maybe the resource(s) can switch to using a topic from the list of common topics
 - term is used in vocabularies of a larger number of resources: “real”/useful topic, consider including as a topic in the list

Demonstrating value via use cases

- Use-cases and impact statements with clear quantitative and qualitative metrics are essential to demonstrate value and justify adoption of the vocabulary
- Use case needs to be able to generate quick returns
- A cross-discipline, cross-resource, cross-community use case would be ideal
- Also want meta-analysis of search paradigms of what users are actually doing - i.e. how people *actually* use the vocabulary
- Need usage metrics, e.g. the number of researchers who have come to a course who would not have found it otherwise: demonstrate discoverability of resources and courses
- Look at search patterns of what people look for: how does this match to how people actually find things (part of answer may lie in vocabulary)

- What is the minimum level of interoperability and linkage between all these different resources for the effort to reach critical mass?

Community engagement

- How do you build and motivate a community to deliver/develop this ontology?
- Need a few flagship resources to adopt it and make the ontology initiative work
- Adoption funds would enable faster adoption
- Carry out annotation sprints, e.g. to facilitate a certain resource adopting a vocabulary and start benefitting from the annotation
- Input mechanism/involvement of community: need to be careful to distinguish between “organisational” mechanism for addition of topics and technical implementation - two different things
- Great expense in curating resources can be made easier: for example, in on-course people adding resources (courses) are currently picking topics from a flat list; what they want to do is auto-lookup from the topics ontology, semi-automation of the annotation process

Funding strategies

- Funding would support development, management and contributions to the common vocabulary
- Specific funding needed to be able to develop and implement the vocabulary:
 - travel expenses
 - workshops
 - online infrastructure for versions, term requests etc.
 - funds for legacy systems to adopt the vocabulary / reannotation of existing resources (a few months of funding and some tools to do this)

- There must be multiple actions including seeking national and international/EC funding
- Upcoming projects (including within ELIXIR) may provide use cases, workflows, services etc.
- Engage journal editors and funders
- Important: common topics enable discoverability, interoperability and impact of resources: not the ontology is funded but the vehicle to advance the usefulness of resources to researchers and, consequently, research

ANNEX 1: Workshop documentation

tinyurl.com/TopicsView Prototype topics vocabulary

tinyurl.com/OurTopicsNotes Workshop Notes (“Living document”)

ANNEX 2: Workshop organisers and sponsors

- Janet Thornton (EMBL-EBI, BioMedBridges)
- Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)
- Søren Brunak (ELIXIR-DK, BioMedBridges, ELIXIR/BioMedBridges Services Registry, CBS-DTU tools)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR-UK, ISBE, TeSS, Fairport, myExperiment, SSI, BioCatalogue, SEEK4Science, FAIRDOM)
- Rob Hooft (ELIXIR-NL, NLeSC, DTL, Fairport)
- Inge Jonassen (ELIXIR-NO, University of Bergen)
- Heinz Stockinger (ELIXIR-CH, SIB, ExPASy)
- Terri Attwood (ELIXIR-UK, BioDBCore, EMBnet, GOBLET, iAnn, ISCB, ISB, AllBio, SeqAhead, TeSS)
- Cath Brooksbank (ELIXIR-UK, EMBL-EBI, EMTRAIN, GOBLET, on-course, TeSS)
- Manuel Corpas (ELIXIR-UK, BioJS, GOBLET, iAnn, ISCB, TeSS)

- Vassilios Ioannidis (ELIXIR-CH, SIB, ExpASy)
- Hervé Ménager (Institut Pasteur, BioWeb2, Mobylye)
- Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI, BioMedBridges, ELIXIR/BioMedBridges Services Registry)
- Francis Rowland (EMBL-EBI, BioJS)
- Susanna-Assunta Sansone (ELIXIR-UK, BioDBCORE, BioSharing, ISA Commons, TeSS; RDA TAB)
- Vicky Schneider (ELIXIR-UK, EMBnet, GOBLET, iAnn, TeSS)

Technical organisers

- Jon Ison (ELIXIR-DK, ELIXIR/BioMedBridges Services Registry, EDAM, Tools@EBI)
- Rafael Jimenez (ELIXIR Hub)
- Stephanie Suhr (EMBL-EBI, BioMedBridges)
- Francis Rowland (EMBL-EBI)

ANNEX 3: Workshop participants

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---|
| ▪ Bengt Persson | ELIXIR Sweden |
| ▪ Brendan Vaughan | EMBL-EBI |
| ▪ Camille Laibe | EMBL-EBI |
| ▪ Carole Goble | The University of Manchester, ELIXIR-UK |
| ▪ Cath Brooksbank | EMBL-EBI, EMTRAIN, ELIXIR-UK |
| ▪ Chris Morris | STFC |
| ▪ Christophe Blanchet | CNRS IFB-core |
| ▪ Dan Bolser | EMBL-EBI |
| ▪ Daniele Pierpaolo Colobraro | MIRRI - USMI |
| ▪ Egon Willighagen | Maastricht University |
| ▪ Emily Angiolini | The Genome Analysis Centre |
| ▪ Francis Rowland | EMBL-EBI |
| ▪ Frederik Coppens | VIB/PSB |
| ▪ Gergely Sipos | EGI.eu (European Grid Infrastructure) |
| ▪ Inge Jonassen | ELIXIR Norway and University of Bergen |

- Jaime Prilusky ELIXIR Israel and Weizmann Institute of Science
- Jean-Francois Gibrat IFB
- Jo McEntyre EMBL-EBI
- Jon Ison ELIXIR-DK
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- Tanya Dickie The Genome Analysis Centre
- Terri Attwood The University of Manchester, ELIXIR-UK
- Marie-Dominique Devignes CNRS and University of Lorraine

ANNEX 4: Registries mapped in preparation for the workshop

Resource	Number of terms used	Number or non-mappable terms	Number of mappable terms	Number of terms mapped
F1000	289	30	259	139
GOBLET	219	82	137	137
ExPASy	156	44	112	105
iAnn	119	33	86	73
On-course®	78	0	78	65
EBI resource keywords	231	153	78	58
AppDB VT vocab subset	104	28	76	66
NIF	130	72	58	48
BioCatalogue categories	85	29	56	55
Metabase + BioRegistry DB categories (NAR DB Issue)	60	12	48	47
Identifiers.org tags	48	8	40	34
BioDiversity categories	54	15	39	23
FigShare Biological Sciences	36	0	36	30
Transplant DB data types	33	8	25	25
EBI website categories	23	1	22	16
Transplant DB keywords	35	13	22	21
BioWIKI types	23	7	16	21
OBO Foundry Categories	22	8	14	11
BitLab topic	16	4	12	12
Open PHACTS Dataset topics	11	0	11	11
BioLinux Categories	18	8	10	10
PathGuide	9	0	9	7
RostLab tool categories	7	0	7	7
DebTags	9	2	7	9
TOTALS	1815	557	1258	1030

Annex 5: Related resources

- PLOS thesaurus: [Thesaurus evolution: a case study in “synthetic biology”](#) (PLOS blogs April 2014), [PLOS thesaurus on GitHub](#). Subject Area terms are related to each other with a system of broader/narrower term relationships; thesaurus structure is a polyhierarchy.
- <http://schema.org>
- BRIF: “The role of a bioresource research impact factor as an incentive to share human bioresources” <http://europepmc.org/abstract/MED/21614086>
- Just Enough Results Model <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/JERM> (used in FAIRDOM for Sys Bio, part of ISBE, EraNets SysMO and EraSysAPP, and the Virtual Liver Network)
- NIH BD2K Data Discovery Index Coordination Consortium (DDICC), named BioCADDIE: <http://biocaddie.org>
- NIH BD2K Centre for Enhanced Data Annotation and Retrieval: <http://metadatacenter.org/>
- The NIH BD2K Software Discovery Index Consortium, to be funded (<http://softwarediscoveryindex.org>).
- [SeqWiki](#)
- [Semantic MediaWiki](#) (SMW) and it's plugin [RDFIO](#)
- [WikiData](#)
- NIF Registry http://www.neuinfo.org/products/nif_registry.shtml
- [NeuroLex](#)
- Tools for building ontologies (Populous <http://www.e-lico.eu/populous.html>) prototyping and annotating content through stealth by spreadsheets (RightField <http://www.rightfield.org.uk>)
- Google spreadsheet based annotation tool OntoMaton: <http://www.isa-tools.org/tools.html>
- Dataset Descriptions: HCLS Community Profile <http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/hcls/notes/hcls-dataset/>
- <http://www.on-course.eu>
- <http://www.fosteropenscience.eu/>
- GFbio terminology server <http://terminologies.gfbio.org/>